

**SUPERCRITICAL FLUID SYNTHESIS OF C-BN AND POLYMORPHES OF BORON NITRIDE
FROM GRAPHITE-LIKE PRECURSORS**

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Abstract

Supercritical fluid synthesis of dense, intermediate and amorphous BN phases has been studied at pressures 50 and 200 MPa and temperature ~ 1000 °K from h-BN and t-BN as precursors and H₂O and N₂ as fluids. According to the results of electron and X-ray diffractions, FTIR and hardness measurement, c-BN phase is proved to be the main synthesized phase with the level of transformation at least 20 %. Two different mechanisms of c-BN nanocrystals formation are proposed. Hardness values of synthesized crystals fill out all scale of hardness: ultrasoft, soft, normal and hard, characterizing several unconventional phases, including E-BN (B₁₂N₁₂).

Keywords: boron nitride, crystal growth, supercritical fluid synthesis, c-BN, electron microscopy, E-BN, X-ray diffraction, hardness.

1. Introduction

Supercritical fluid synthesis is a universal method for a high-pressure high-temperature synthesis of different oxides, sulfides, nitrides, carbon phases etc. [1-6] and self-assembling of nanomaterials [7]. Advantageous of this method is that the different gases used in the supercritical fluid synthesis can play the roles of a medium for creating pressure (He, Ar), a solvent and a chemical reagent (H₂, N₂, H₂O, CO₂ etc.). Dissolving capacity of fluids is rapidly increased with increasing of the pressure, that is important also for supercritical fluid extraction. On the other hand, the velocity of crystal growth in supercritical medium is increased up to 0.1-0.3 mm/h, which at least five times greater than that for hydrothermal methods. Moreover, crystals raised from the gas phases have a high degree of perfection, in comparison with crystals obtained from liquid or solid phases.

Cubic boron nitride (c-BN) is known to be the one of the best industrial abrasive and cutting materials, combining wear resistance, high hardness and thermal stability. It is widely used in electronics due to chemical and mechanical stability, high electrical insulating properties, optical transparency etc. [8,9]. Judging from conditions of synthesis, c-BN synthesis can be divided on the next general ways: a) extreme shock-wave synthesis ($P > 5$ GPa) [10], a) high-pressure high temperature solid-state synthesis in anvil apparatus ($5 \text{ GPa} > P > 1 \text{ GPa}$, $T > 1000$ °C) [11-13] b) intermediate condition of synthesis ($0.1 \text{ MPa} < P < 5 \text{ GPa}$, 300 °C $< T < 1000$ °C), i.e. supercritical fluid [2-4] or hydro- [14,15] and benzene- [16] thermal syntheses and c) ambient pressure synthesis, i.e. plasma electrolysis method ($P \sim 0.1$

MPa, $T \sim 300$ 0K) [17], d) vacuum synthesis, i.e. chemical and physical vapor deposition (CVD and PVD), pulsed laser deposition (PLD) etc. ($P < 0.1$ MPa, 200 °C $< T < 1200$ °C) [18,19].

According to phase diagram of boron nitride, c-BN is a stable phase at ambient pressure (see for details [4,20]), and transformation of c-BN to a graphitic form of hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) becomes possible only at temperatures ~ 2000 °K [21] and ~ 2700 °K at pressure of 5 GPa [13]. Recent studies indicate that aggregates of c-BN and wurtzite-like BN (w-BN) fill up the “gap of hardness” between c-BN and diamond with the absolute value of hardness of 85 GPa [13]. Since c-BN is a stable phase, its synthesis could be possible both from reagents [14-16], or from graphite-like precursors [10-13]. Therefore, scientific and industrial interests to dense and unconventional forms of BN, including both synthetic routes and properties, will only increase with the time.

The aim of this work is to synthesize at different conditions of supercritical fluid synthesis and to investigate the received samples of boron nitride. It should be noted that Solozhenko et al. [2-4] synthesized using this method c-BN at $P > 2$ GPa and $T > 1000$ °K over catalyst. At ambient pressure only epitaxial growth of c-BN was observed at diamond grains without nucleation of c-BN. At hydrothermal conditions, c-BN crystals as large as 0.5 mm with defects could be synthesized from the reagents [14].

2. Experimental details

Equipment for supercritical fluid synthesis represents reactors with an inner holder for the samples, aggregates for compressions and cleaning of gas, heating system, and automatic control system. The equipment

allows to create for the short time (0.5-1h) and to keep for the long time (hours, days) the gas pressures up to 1 GPa [1,5].

Details of experimental equipment are presented in Fig.1. Gas from the balloon (1) under a pressure of 50–150 atm enters the gas compressor (5), where it is

compressed to a pressure of 200–2000 atm and under this pressure is fed into the reactor (9). After that, the high pressure valve (8) cuts off the reactor from the gas system of the equipment. The heating of the furnace ensures a further increase in pressure in the reactor during the experiment.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the equipment: 1 — gas balloon; 2 — low pressure valve; 3 — low pressure manometer; 5 — gas compressor up to 2000 atm; 6, 7 — high pressure manometer; 4, 8 — high pressure valves; 9 — reactor; 10 — electronic control unit.

In the first experiment industrial h-BN (Zaporozhsky abrasivny kombinat, goint stock company, Ukraine) was used as a precursor and water as a fluid without additional gas pressure ($P \sim 50$ MPa, $T \sim 1000$ °K). In the second experiment domestic turbostratic boron nitride (t-BN) was used a precursor and water as a fluid with nitrogen gas pressure ($P = 0.2$ GPa, $T \sim 1000$ °K). In the third experiment industrial h-BN was treated with the scheme of the second experiment.

Electron diffraction patterns were obtained at room temperature with a Philips EM-400T transmission electron microscope (TEM), using an acceleration voltage of 100 kV. The samples were prepared by dispersal of the synthesized crystallites in ethanol, and subsequent deposition on a grid containing holes [22]. The diffraction patterns were evaluated by measuring of the distance between pairs of appropriately chosen reciprocal points or diameters of rings in the photographs. The elemental composition of the grains under investigation was analyzed qualitatively using the spectrometer attached to the TEM.

IR spectra of powder samples were measured in the region of $5000\text{--}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature using the KBr method with a Bruker IFSS/66v FTIR spectrometer under vacuum conditions.

Hardness measurements were performed at room temperature with a PMT-3 pyramidal diamond indenter

[5]. More than 20 crystals from the second experiment were glued at the plane of semispherical tooth cement matrix with a hardness of 6 GPa, and after that the crystal containing plane was polished for extending of available squares for indentation. Several measurements were made at each of these crystals with three discrete values of loading force, namely 0.196, 0.49 and 0.98 N.

X-ray diffraction patterns were received with the powder methods on the DRON-2 diffractometer in the range of $2^{\circ}\text{--}92^{\circ}$ (2θ , $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation) with the step of 0.05° .

3. Results

All samples have been scraped away from the surface of inner holder, namely from the zone of the gas transfer of substances. Distributions of electron diffraction spots at Fig. 2 have an original nature, so that it could not be attributed to single phases. Moreover, the spots are arranged not only in the single spots and circles but also in ellipsoids (see Table 1). There are hundreds of crystals from different phases and in different orientations. Qualitative analysis of the element composition using the spectrometer reveals only light elements (B, C, N, O) in the samples under investigations. Additionally, Fe is detected on one of needle-like samples.

Fig. 2. Electron diffraction patterns taken from different samples of the same zone of inner holder of reactor, containing grains of untransformed h-BN (Sample №1) (a) and synthesized c-BN (Sample №2) (b). The main hkl planes for phase identifications are added, showing direct transformation of h-BN to a denser form of BN.

Table 1.

Interpretation of electron diffraction patterns from Fig.1.

Sample №2			Sample №1			Interpretation [38]	
D, mm	d-value, Å	Notice	D, mm	d-value, Å	Notice	d-value, Å	Phase
16.5	3.420	Weak ring	16.5	3.420	Strong spots	3.331	(002) hBN, (003) rBN
26.2	2.153	Ring	26.2	2.153	Ellipse	2.169	(100) hBN
26.5	2.128		26.5	2.128		2.119	(101) rBN
26.8	2.104		26.8	2.104		2.10	(10) tBN
27.0	2.089	Strong spots on ellipse I	27.0	2.089		2.087	(111) cBN
27.5	2.051		27.5	2.051		2.062	(101) hBN
28.5	1.979		-	-	-	1,990	(012) rBN
30.8	1.831	Weak spots on ellipse I	-	-	-	1.818	(102) hBN
-	-		-	-	-	1.808	(200) cBN
-	-		33.0	1.709	Weak spots	1,665	(004) hBN, (006) rBN
45.3	1.245	Strong spots on ring	45.3	1.245	Ellipse	1.250	(110) hBN, rBN
48.0	1.175	Broad ring	47.7	1.182		1.278	(220) cBN
52.7	1.070	Ellipse	52.5	1.074	Weak ring	1.172	(112) hBN, (113) rBN
52.5	1.074					1.071	(201) hBN, (021) rBN, (311) cBN
69.6	0.812	Ellipse	-	-		1.090	
70.0	0.806					0.808	(420) cBN
78.0	0.723	Ellipse	78.4	0.719	Weak ring	0.723	(500) cBN
78.5	0.719						
91.0	0.620		90.4	0.624	Weak ring	0.629	(441) cBN

Interpretation of reciprocal spaces clearly indicates on the presence of the rhombohedral boron nitride (r-BN), c-BN and, possibly, t-BN in the synthesized samples, as shown in Tab.1. This can indirectly prove that the transformation of h-BN to c-BN in supercritical fluid can be occurred through intermediate r-BN or t-BN phases. Really, r-BN proved to be an intermediate phase between amorphous BN and c-BN within thin BN film structure produced by magnetron dispersion of h-BN target [23], and highly disordered t-BN phase in

the transition region between h-BN and c-BN [12,19]. Moreover, theoretical calculation also indicated, that the activation energy of the r-BN to c-BN transition is eight times lower than that of h-BN to c-BN one (0.5 eV versus 4 eV) [24].

IR-spectra of h-BN before and after supercritical fluid treatment are presented at Fig. 3. Two main absorption peaks at about 815 cm^{-1} and 1375 cm^{-1} correlate with out-of-plane bending and in-plane stretching vibrations of h-BN, respectively [8].

Fig. 3. IR-spectra of untransformed h-BN (dotted line) and synthesized powder (solid line). The most intensive peaks are out of range of figures, however for analysis their intensities were fitted to the values of 10 a.u. An inset highlights the details of IR-spectra. For comparison, the experimental IR-spectrum of c-BN is superimposed in an inset. Arrows indicate the experimental and theoretical bands of c-BN.

Furthermore, peaks at about 1050 cm^{-1} and 1120 cm^{-1} correlate with experimental IR-spectra of c-BN (see inset of Fig.3). There are at about ten bands in the fine structure of c-BN IR-spectrum characterized by Chrenko [25]. Several of these bands are clearly visible in IR-spectrum of the synthesized sample, namely $1000\text{-}1200$, 1590 , 1740 , 2330 , 2530 , and 2920 cm^{-1} , as shown at Fig.3. Since bands at 2330 and 2530 cm^{-1} are presented in the untransformed powder of h-BN, it could be attributed to both c-BN and impurity phase, for instance boron acid, which is discovered in the powders of h-BN. Others should be considered as bands of synthesized c-BN phase.

According to intensity of IR-spectra, c-BN co-exists with h-BN in the ratio from 1:7 to 1:5 with several percent of boron acid as impurity, which could be received from hydrolysis of boron oxide, existing in the h-BN powders with the value less than 0.2%.

Table 2 represents the results of the hardness tests for grains of different structures, properties and colors (see short specification for each grain). The grain sizes are ranged from the smallest of $5\text{-}10\ \mu\text{m}$ (№1, №10) up to the largest of $0.1\text{-}0.2\text{ mm}$ in size (№8, №14). The results are ordered by increasing of the averaged hardness from the minimum ultrasoft value ($\sim 0.18\text{ GPa}$) to the maximum superhard one ($\sim 46.2\text{ GPa}$). Undoubtedly these two extreme values of hardness can be associated with h-BN and c-BN, respectively. Others could be attributed to at least six unknown unconventional intermediate crystal forms of boron nitride or amorphous BN, namely $U_2\text{-}U_7$, because presence of other elements in the grains under examination is limited to several percent [5]. Possibly only whisker-like ultrasoft U_1 phase is composed from iron or iron oxide.

Table 2.

Results of hardness measurements for a set of grain (№1-№15) from the wall of inner holder of reactor after treatment of t-BN in water and nitrogen fluids at P~200 MPa and T~1000 °K.

Grain №	Specification	Hardness, GPa ¹			Averaged hardness, GPa	Phase interpretation
		Point 1	Point 2	Point 3		
2	two sintered spherical grains	0.29 (II)	0.107 (II)	0.155 (I)	0.18	Graphite-like BN
4	yellow	0.184 (II)			0.18	Graphite-like BN
10	black whisker	0.231 (II)			0.23	U ₁
12-A	gray			0.364 (II)	0.36	U ₂
9	steel-gray	0.32 (II)	0.413 (I)		0.37	U ₂
13	pink	0.635 (II)	X ²		0.64	U ₃
6	elastic	0.75 (II)	0.544 (II)	X	0.65	U ₃
5	elastic, pink-gray	0 ³ (I)	1.054 (II)		1.05	U ₄
1	elastic	1.41 (I)			1.41	U ₅ , E-BN
12-B	pink-gray	1.76 (II)	1.37 (II)		1.56	U ₅ , E-BN
14	gray	1.44 (II)	1.22 (II)	2.35 (II)	1.67	U ₅ , E-BN
11	elastic, gray-pink	1.76 (II)	1.96 (I)		1.86	U ₅ , E-BN
3	clear imprint	2.38 (II)	1.99 (II)		2.19	U ₅ , E-BN
7	transparent	0 (II)	2.74 (I)	X (III)	2.74	U ₆ , amorphous BN
15-A	steel-bright	2.90 (I)			2.90	U ₆ , amorphous BN
15-B	steel-bright		8.57 (II)		8.57	U ₇
8	pink-gray	61.8 (I)	39.2 (III)	37.7 (III)	46.2	Cubic boron nitride

¹ a loading force is indicated in brackets (I - 0.196 N, II - 0.49 N, III - 0.98 N).

² the grain has been crashed.

³ the imprint is not visible.

The hardness values for the pairs of different points of grains №12 and №15 differ for three times. Such a difference is not characteristic for hardness of the same material. Therefore, it could be supposed that these grains contain at least two different phases, A and B (see Tab.2). For comparison, the hardness values for ten points of U₅ phase, which fall into soft interval of hardness scale, differ in less than two times. Unconventional U₅ phase is possibly E-BN ($\rho=2.55$ g/cm³) [26], having both diamond-like and zeolite-like nature [27-30]. In such a case E-BN really became so-called intermediate BN phase both on density and hardness.

Most likely, that brittle and transparent phase is amorphous BN, because its hardness is close to the hardness of glass [31], and other semitransparent and brownish grains from the same experiment reveal a non-crystalline structure on X-ray diffraction patterns. Both grains of U₆ phase have the intermediate values of hardness and brittle nature, so that it could be amorphous or glass-like BN. U₇ phase has the highest value of hardness among unconventional forms of BN under

investigation, approaching to the hard values on the scale of hardness. According to assumptions, these phases can be crystallized from amorphous U₆ phase, which co-exists in the same grain.

U₂, U₃ and U₄ phases fall into soft region on the scale of hardness. The total exposure time of the second experiment is about four times greater than that of two others, which can explain a strong variation of synthesized phases.

Table 3 represents the results of analysis of the X-ray diffraction patterns from the third experiment. Most likely c-BN is badly-crystalline as the distant order is broken, that is visible from the broadening of all lines. This pattern shows an intermediate stage of c-BN formation from an amorphous phase, because the lattice is a little bit widened (~1%), especially in distant orders (~1.8%). According to integral intensity c-BN co-exists with amorphous phase in the ratio from 1:5 to 1:3 with several percent of other impurities, the most possibly fullerenes of BN, B₁₂N₁₂ [32,33,37], clusters of unconventional phases and h-BN.

Table 3.

Results of powder X-ray diffraction for sediments on the wall of reactor from the third experiment

2θ , $\text{CuK}\alpha$	Specification	d-value, nm	Intensity	Interpretation [38]	
				hkl	Phase (δ , %)
11.3 ⁰	Peak	0.782	10	-	fullerenes of BN
21.0 ⁰	haloe	0.423	90	-	Amorphous BN
42.75 ⁰	peak+haloe	0.211	100	111	c-BN (+1.1)
44.15 ⁰	peak	0.205	10	101	h-BN (-0.6)
49.5 ⁰	haloe	0.184	20	200	c-BN (+1.8)
72.6 ⁰	haloe	0.1301	10	220	c-BN (+1.8)
87.8 ⁰	haloe	0.1108	10	311	c-BN (+1.7)

Conclusions

To conclude, t-BN is shown to be the most reactive substance, because more than ten different phases are observed after treatment on the base of hardness measurements. Additionally, h-BN does not undergo full transformation to denser form. All data indicate that transformation to c-BN averages from 10 to 30 percent at the given parameters of syntheses. These values lie below in comparison with the supercritical fluid synthesis at the range of pressure 2-5 GPa and temperature 900-1600 °K over catalysts [2-4]. Conditions of our syntheses are still more forthcoming to the line of equilibrium c-BN with h-BN, therefore it is necessary to expect a reduction of c-BN nucleation. Nevertheless, in the present work for the first time the high level of nucleation of c-BN is observed without additional catalysts, excluding fluids themselves.

On the basis of received results two different mechanisms of c-BN nucleation in fluids could be proposed. At the first one, h-BN undergoes transformations to r-BN, which undergoes further transformations to c-BN. In this case the direct solid-solid diffusion mechanism predominates. At the second one, h-BN or t-BN are dissolved in the fluids and re-crystallize into c-BN by mechanism of incongruent melting. It is easy to explain the differences of hardness from the same unknown phase by the differences of crystallization level from point to point of the sample. At direct transition the degree of transformation appears lower, than that at crystallization from an amorphous phase, what could be explained by different kinetics of phase transition.

We did not study the morphology of synthesized c-BN closer: it appears as nanocrystals of 3-30 nm in sizes, like in [34,35].

Absence of w-BN in the products of synthesis indirectly confirms an assumption that w-BN in contrast to c-BN is a metastable phase at the chosen parameters of synthesis. The same results were obtained during CVD synthesis of c-BN with only c-BN, h-BN and t-BN phases in synthesized thin films [36] and composites [39]. The results show that, the use of water fluid as both reagent and catalyst leads to diminishing the threshold pressure value of the of c-BN nucleation.

A set of new experiments, in particular, with different P-T parameters of synthesis and time of treatments are planned to carry out for receiving the details of phase transitions, and for production of novel unconventional phases as much as possible.

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